

Responsible Development of Neurotechnology

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IMPACT OF NEUROTECHNOLOGY

WHAT?

- Systems that measure, process & modulate brain activity
- Intimately related to self & personhood, entailing new & different types of impact on individuals

WHEN?

- All stages of product cycles
- Ideation
- Design
- Validation
- Deployment
- Operation

WHO?

- International Organisations
- Government & Regulators
- Standard Development Organizations
- Industry & Businesses
- Academia & Innovators
- NGOs & Patient Associations
- Users of Consumer Applications

RISK MITIGATION MEASURES

PRESERVING COGNITIVE LIBERTY

WHY?

- Protect Self-Determination
- Avoid Manipulation
- Preserve Personality & Identity

HOW?

- Regulation Defining Acceptable Use Cases & Competences
- Continuous Risk Monitoring Mechanisms
- User-centred Strategies
- Ethics-by-Design Principles

PROTECTING BRAIN DATA

WHY?

- Sensitive & Personal Information
- Privacy Invasion
- Profiling & Discrimination

HOW?

- Data Ownership Frameworks & Processes
- Privacy-by-Design Principle
- Data Sovereignty Safeguard